

Clustering analysis for pervaporation performance assessment of alginate hybrid membranes in dehydration of ethanol

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ABSTRACT

Pervaporative dehydration of 96 vol% ethanol solution was used as an experimental model for the determination of hybrid alginate membranes separation performance. Series of membranes filled with different metal oxides particles (magnetite, zinc, silver, titanium(IV) and chromium(III) oxide) were prepared and the effect of the oxide's nature and filling ratio on pervaporative transport and separation effectiveness was discussed. Hierarchical agglomerative cluster analysis of the evaluated parameters was applied to divide all membranes into four clusters, with the most effective comprising of 10 and 15 wt% magnetite loaded for which Pervaporative Separation Index reached the value of 56.79 and 76.59, respectively.

KEYWORDS

Ethanol dehydration, hybrid membranes, pervaporation, sodium alginate, metal oxides

1. Introduction

Energy is one of the most important factors that limit the economic and industrial developments. The increase of the world's population entails an increase in the production and consumption of goods whose manufacturing, transport and usage are associated with an enormous increase in an energy demand. Furthermore, the variations of oil cost and its limited resources in many countries lead to the urgent need to look for the new sources of energy [1-3]. Ethanol has many favourable physiochemical properties which make it the preferred alternative to gasoline. Alcohols mixed with gasoline also allow to reduce the pollutant emissions and fossil fuel consumption. Due to the fact that their molecules contain oxygen atoms in the structure, the obtained fuel is highly volatile as well as allows to obtain higher compression ratio that, consequently, increases a thermal efficiency and decreases emission of gases which are harmful to the environment. Since 2000, the total energy consumption in the global transportation sector has been increasing 2 % annually, and the global ethanol production has risen from 28.5 billion litres in 2004 up to 98 billion litres in 2015 [4-6].

Furthermore, ethanol is one of the most important and common organic substrate that can be easily transformed via dehydration process into numerous compounds such as diethyl ether, ethylene and higher hydrocarbons. Due to the formation of an azeotrope with water (at ~96 vol% concentration of ethanol under atmospheric pressure), the complete removal of water is impossible in the conventional distillation process. As an alternative, the pervaporation (PV) technologies have been actively used in various industries during the last decades [7-9].

In pervaporation process, the separation performance and the stability of membrane is the key issue for its application [10-15]. Based on the solution-diffusion model, the separation process is achieved by the differences in a solubility and diffusivity of the feed components in the membrane material. PV can be applied in the three fields classified as follows: the

dehydration of aqueous - organic mixtures; the removal of organic compounds from organic - aqueous mixtures; and the separation of organic - organic mixtures. Dehydration of organic solvents is the most important application of pervaporation, since its first commercial application was the dehydration of ethanol using a hybrid system with a distillation column. For the dehydration of organic solvents, hydrophilic membranes are commonly used, mainly because of the favourable water solubility and diffusivity in the hydrophilic matrix, resulting in the increased selective permeation of water. Many researchers have been making continuous efforts to develop the new polymeric membranes. Recently, several reports have been published in the literature on the use of the different types of hydrophilic polymers including poly(vinyl alcohol) [13, 16-17], sodium alginate [13,15,18-19] and chitosan [15, 20-22]. However, membranes developed using this type of materials suffer from the insufficient mechanical strength and chemical instability in an aqueous solutions mainly due to the excessive swelling. This could be overcome by the applying of crosslinking process [21-23], preparation of polymer blends [24-25], formation of hybrid organic – inorganic composite membranes [15,20-21,26], chemical modification through grafting with some hydrophilic polymers [27-28], and formation of a thin and dense separation layer on the top of porous substrates. Among these, the organic–inorganic hybrids are an emerging class of innovative nanostructured materials with tailored properties and unparalleled performances suitable for the wide range of practical applications. Considering aforementioned, we have investigated the series of organic–inorganic alginate hybrid membranes crosslinked by calcium chloride and filled with five metal oxide, *i.e.* Fe₃O₄, ZnO, Ag₂O, Cr₂O₃ and TiO₂. Choice of the above oxides was related to the fact that they are widely used as a filler for the different types of hybrid membranes and beads, and applied in several separation processes but usually are not compared directly [29]. Because of different tendency toward the formation of hydroxide layer these oxides promise to exhibit a different impact on the separation properties and

stability of the membranes during the pervaporative dehydration of ethanol. Three oxides, *i.e.* magnetite, silver and zinc oxide, have a particle size in the range of 2-30 nm. The mean diameter of the other two is between 80-110 nm. Additionally, iron oxide owns intrinsic magnetic properties that, according to our previous research, should favourably contribute to the PV separation efficiency [18-19] and vapour permeation [20-21, 30] in the ethanol/water system.

The physicochemical properties of the resulting membranes were studied by FTIR spectroscopy, wide-angle X-ray diffraction measurements and SEM. The membranes were successfully employed for the PV separation of water-ethanol mixture. The values of flux, and both water and ethanol permeation coefficients were determined, from which, afterwards, the selectivity coefficient, separation factor and pervaporation separation index (*PSI*) were calculated. Additionally, based on the hierarchical cluster analysis of transport descriptors the investigated membranes were grouped into four clusters consisting of the most closely related objects. The isolation of homogeneous groups facilitated the determination of their essential characteristics and helped to indicate membranes with the best performance.

2. Experimental

2.1 Materials

Sodium alginate (Brookfield viscosity 350 to 550 mPa·s, $c = 1$ wt% at 20 °C) was obtained from Acros Organic. $\text{FeCl}_2 \cdot 4\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (purity $\geq 98\%$), anhydrous FeCl_3 puriss p.a., anhydrous sodium acetate puriss p.a., zinc acetate (purity $\geq 99\%$), silver nitrate puriss p.a. and sodium hydroxide puriss p.a. used in the preparation of metal oxide nanoparticles were purchased from Sigma-Aldrich company. Calcium chloride (purity $\geq 96\%$) applied as crosslinker, were purchased from Avantor S.A. Five metal oxide were used for membrane preparation; three of them, *i.e.* iron(II,III) oxide, zinc(II) oxide and silver(I) oxide were

synthesised by in situ alkaline salt hydrolysis and precipitation method; additional two, *i.e.* titanium(IV) oxide and chromium(III) oxide were purchased from Sigma-Aldrich and used as received.

2.2 Preparation of iron, silver and zinc oxides

Iron oxide particles were prepared based on the Das modified method [31]. Briefly, 12 g of $\text{FeCl}_2 \cdot 4\text{H}_2\text{O}$ and 18 g of anhydrous FeCl_3 were separately dissolved in 50 ml of water then mixed together in a 600 ml beaker with subsequent addition of 50 ml of concentrated ammonium hydroxide solution (24 wt%) and stirred for 4 hours. The decanted precipitate was washed twice by mixing with a diluted ammonium hydroxide solution (5 wt%). After the second washing, the volume of precipitate slurry was adjusted to 50 ml and 4 g of dodecanoic (lauric) acid was added. The mixture was continuously stirred and heated for two minutes using 550 W laboratory heating plate. Obtained stable magnetic fluid was filtered and dried at room temperature. Before using it for membrane preparation, solid magnetite was finely ground in agate mortar and redispersed in polymer solution using ultrasonic bath.

Zinc oxide particles were synthesized according to Dakhlaoui et al., using the zinc acetate and sodium hydroxide as the starting materials [32]. In this case, 0.439 g of $\text{Zn}(\text{CH}_3\text{COO})_2$ was dissolved in 50 ml of a deionised water, stirred and heated at 80 °C. Next, 5 ml of 0.2 M sodium hydroxide solution was added drop-wise. After addition of NaOH, stirring and heating of the precipitated slurry was continued for further 30 min. The solid particles were washed several times with water and ethanol, and separated from the solvent using the centrifuge. After last centrifugation, the product was dried in an oven at 50 °C for 12 hours and finally ground in a mortar. White, free flowing powder of ZnO was obtained.

Silver oxide particles were prepared based on Sullivan modified method [33]. Thus, 0.1359 g of silver nitrate was dissolved in 160 ml of deionised water. The obtained aqueous solution was stirred vigorously at 60 °C to give a transparent solution. 20 ml of 0.025 M

sodium hydroxide was added drop-wise to the resultant solution. Stirring and heating was continued for an additional hour. Solid particles were washed several times with water and ethanol, and separated from the solvent using the centrifuge. After last centrifugation, the product was dried in an oven at 50 °C for 12 hours and finally ground in a mortar obtaining brown Ag₂O nanoparticles.

The size and particle size distribution of the prepared nanoparticles was determined by the DLS technique and confirmed also by the TEM and BET measurements. The purity of the phase of the synthesized oxides was determined by the powder XRD analysis.

2.3 Membrane preparation

1.5 wt% sodium alginate solution was prepared by dissolving an appropriate amount of sodium alginate in a deionised water. Afterward this solution was mixed with an appropriate portion of metal oxide particles, to receive 5; 10 or 15 wt% concentration of inorganic fillers in membrane, respectively. After sonification, the homogenous sodium alginate solution was casted onto Petri dishes levelled on glass plate, and slowly evaporated to dryness at 40 °C. After 24 h, the formed membrane was crosslinked by immersing in 2.5 mol% calcium chloride solution for 120 min at room temperature. The pristine membrane was prepared in the same manner as above except of the addition of metal oxide particles.

2.4 Membrane characterization and instrumental analysis

Prepared nanoparticles and membranes were characterized using scanning electron microscope (SEM), transmission electron microscope (TEM), Brunauer–Emmett–Teller (BET) adsorption method, powder X-ray diffraction (XRD) measurements and FTIR spectroscopy. FTIR spectra were measured using the Perkin Elmer Spectrum Two FTIR spectrometer in ATR mode (Diamond UATR 1-reflection accessory, PerkinElmer Inc., USA)

at ambient temperature. The spectral range was 650-4000 cm^{-1} and the spectral resolution 2 cm^{-1} . Metal oxide powder samples were placed on a slightly disoriented monocrystalline silicon plate and subjected to XRD analysis using a Philips X'Pert diffractometer provided with a Cu K-alpha X-rays source ($\lambda = 1.542 \text{ \AA}$). Measurements were carried out in the θ - 2θ Bragg-Brentano geometry in reflection mode at the 25-75° 2θ range. The data were analysed using the HighScore Plus[®] software packages with ICDD PDF-4+ database for the phase identification (PANalytical Inc., USA). SEM characterization was done using a Phenom Pro-X microscope equipped with the 3D Roughness Reconstruction software and energy dispersive X-ray analyser (EDS) (Phenom-World B.V., The Netherlands). TEM studies of the oxide nanoparticles were performed using a Tecnai F20 TWIN microscope (FEI Company) equipped with a field emission gun and operated at an acceleration voltage of 200 kV. Images were recorded on the Eagle 4K camera using dedicated Imaging and Analysing software. Specimen preparation was done by a rapid vitrification of the small drop of oxide's aqueous dispersion placed on the Ti grid by plunging it into liquid ethane. Pictures were processed using a ImageJ public domain software. The structural parameters of synthesized oxides were determined from nitrogen adsorption/desorption isotherms measured at 77 K in an automatic Micromeritics ASAP 2020 apparatus prior evacuation and degassing of the samples for 24 hours at 383 K under reduced pressure. The specific surface area (SBET) was calculated for p/p^0 in the range of 0.05-0.25, using Brunauer-Emmet-Teller (BET) method. The D50 diameter and particle size distribution of the prepared oxide nanoparticles was determined by DLS method using a Malvern Instruments Zetasizer Nano ZS90. The membrane thickness was measured using waterproof precise coating thickness gauge MG-401 ELMETRON, and was estimated as a mean values of at least 10 repetition in different points and was found to equal $22.0 \pm 1.2 \mu\text{m}$.

2.5 Pervaporation experiments

PV experiments were carried out using the apparatus described in our previous paper [19]. As a feed, the aqueous solution of 96 vol% ethanol was used. The permeate was condensed and collected in a cold trap cooled with a liquid nitrogen. The suitable fluxes were calculated from the measured weight of collected permeates in the trap for a given time interval at a steady-state condition. The composition of feed, permeate and retentate streams was analysed by means of gas chromatography [19]. For each membrane the PV measurement was repeated three times. The results showed good repeatability and the order of magnitude of errors did not exceed 3 %. The permeation flux (J) of i component was calculated using the following equation [34-35]:

$$J_i = \frac{m_i}{At} \quad (1)$$

where m_i – is a weight of component i in permeate, kg, A – an effective membrane area, m^2 , t – a permeation time, hr.

Two parameters were used for the description of the separation properties of membrane, namely the separation factor (α_{AB}) and selectivity coefficient (S_{CAB}). The separation factor was calculated by following equation [34-35]:

$$\alpha_{AB} = \frac{y_A / y_B}{x_A / x_B} \quad (2)$$

where x_A, x_B – a weight fraction of components in the feed, wt%, y_A, y_B – a weight fraction of components in permeate, wt%.

Based on the first Fick's law, the permeation coefficient can be determined according to the formula:

$$P = \frac{Q_{STP} \cdot l}{\Delta p \cdot A} \quad (3)$$

where P – is a permeation coefficient, Barrer, Q_{STP} – a flow rate at standard conditions, $\text{cm}^3_{STP} \cdot \text{s}^{-1}$, l – a membrane thickness, cm, A – a membrane active area, cm^2 , Δp – a difference of vapour pressure at both sides of membrane, cmHg.

The flow rate at the standard condition is defined as:

$$Q_{STP} = Q \cdot \frac{T_{STP} \cdot p}{T \cdot p_{STP}} \quad (4)$$

where Q – is measured flow rate, $\text{m}^3 \cdot \text{s}^{-1}$, p – an atmospheric pressure, Pa, T – an atmospheric temperature, K, p_{STP} – a standard pressure, $p_{STP} = 1.013 \cdot 10^5 \text{Pa}$, T_{STP} – a standard temperature, $T_{STP} = 298,15 \text{K}$.

The selectivity coefficient is equal to the ratio of permeability of separated components [34-35]:

$$SC_{AB} = \frac{P_A}{P_B} \quad (5)$$

In order to compare the separation efficiency of investigated membranes, the pervaporation separation index expressed (PSI) by following equation [34-35] was used:

$$PSI = J(\alpha_{AB} - 1) \quad (6)$$

where J – a total permeate flux, $\text{kg} \cdot \text{m}^{-2} \cdot \text{hr}^{-1}$, α_{AB} – a separation factor.

2.6 Hierarchical cluster analysis method

Clustering is a method of unsupervised learning classification, used for grouping elements into the relatively homogeneous sets. The similarity between elements (expressed by similarity or distance functions) constitutes the basis for grouping of the most algorithms. Cluster analysis is based on the principle that distances between pairs of points (i.e. cases) in the measurement space are inversely related to their degree of similarity. Clustering consists in the isolation of groups (classes, subsets), each being a collection of objects that are similar

to each other and unlike the objects from other groups [36]. A k-means clustering method belongs to a group of non-hierarchical algorithms. The main difference between non-hierarchical and hierarchical algorithms is the need to prioritize the number of clusters. This method is used to create distinctly different k-clusters. The algorithm consists of moving the objects from cluster to cluster until they are optimized for the intra-cluster and between clusters variations. It is obvious that the similarity in a cluster should be as strong as possible, whereas other groups should be maximally different from one another. Non-hierarchical cluster analysis methods begin with a defined number of clusters and consider variation in the objects locations in order to find a location with the optimum assessment function of the clustering. Hierarchical cluster analysis methods gradually join objects or divide an initial cluster composed of all objects, and enable a convenient graphical representation of the entire sequence of clustering/dividing of clusters. Because of its similarity to the tree, the resulting graphical representation is called a dendrogram. The data groups are obtained by truncating the dendrogram at any level. Cluster analysis is based on the principle that distances between pairs of points (i.e. cases) in the measurement space are inversely related to their degree of similarity. The hierarchical cluster analysis starts with each case (a type of membrane) as a separate cluster (*i.e.* there are as many clusters as cases), and then combines the clusters sequentially, reducing its number at each step until only one cluster is left. The closest two points in a data set are selected. The selection is made on the basis of the Euclidean distance. The Euclidean distance is the best choice for a distance metric in the hierarchical clustering because the interpoint distances between the samples can be computed directly. The selected points are linked and from this moment on, they will be treated as a one point. The linkage criterion determines the distance between sets of cases as a function of the pair wise distances between observations. In this case it is complete-linkage clustering [36-38]. A generated dendrogram shows the linkage points: the clusters are linked at increasing levels of

dissimilarity. Methods used in our research are based both on the agglomeration and the k-means method.

3. Results and discussion

3.1 Material characterization

3.1.1 FTIR analysis

The investigation of surface functional groups was carried out using ATR FTIR analysis for non-crosslinked and crosslinked with calcium chloride alginate membranes and is shown in Fig. 1. It is observed that the crosslinking with Ca^{2+} ions does not affect notably the chemical structure of alginate. It is known that the ionic interactions of the polymer chains with calcium cations entail formation of electronegative cavities, and result in cross-linking of the chains into an “egg box” structure [39]. All main vibration states of the polymer chain are preserved and present in both spectra. The existence of the peaks around 3400 cm^{-1} and 1600 cm^{-1} is related to the stretching of hydroxyl and carboxyl groups, respectively, existing in alginate chains. Presence of Ca^{2+} ions enhances the hydrophilicity of the matrix and is manifested by the noticeable increase in the -O-H stretching band. Furthermore, exchange of monovalent sodium cations with divalent calcium ones in the alginate’s carboxyl groups significantly shifts the stretching vibration of the -C=O group from 1618 to 1590 cm^{-1} .

Fig. 1. ATR FTIR spectra of sodium alginate powder (Alg) and alginate membrane crosslinked with divalent calcium cations (AlgCa).

The ATR FTIR spectra of pristine alginate membrane and membranes loaded with 10 wt% metal oxides are compared in the figure S1. As it can be seen, the bands of polymer matrix that appear in the spectrum of pristine membrane, are also visible in the case of spectra of membranes containing the metal oxides. No noticeable red or blue peaks shifts are observed, indicating lacks of a strong interaction between fillers and polymer matrix.

3.1.2 Structural analysis of metal oxide particles

The structure of the three synthesized metal oxides was confirmed by XRD measurements as shown in the Fig.2. Concerning Ag₂O samples, structural refinement of the XRD data reveals that they crystallized in the nearly single phase with cubic crystallographic cell. The sample showed two strong X-ray diffraction peaks at $2\theta = 32.9^\circ$ (111) and 38.1° (200) and several weak peaks at 55.0° (220), 65.8° (311) and 69.0° (222). The positions of the peaks are in good agreement with literature values (ICCD Card No: 00-001-1041). From the X-rays

diffractogram, we found an average crystallite size of 19.2 ± 4.5 nm as given by the Scherrer formula.

The XRD pattern of magnetite Fe_3O_4 was identified as the only phase in prepared magnetite sample. Any other possible phases were not identified by XRD analysis. The XRD diffractogram shows peak characteristics indexed to magnetite with face-centered cubic phase Fd-3m, (ICCD Card No: 00-011-0614). Prominent peaks that matched the magnetite phase are 30.1° (220), 35.5° (311), 43.2° (400), 57.0° (511) and 62.6° (440) [40]. For this oxide, the measured crystallite size is 42.3 ± 7.5 nm.

Fig.2. Powder X-rays profiles of synthesized oxides.

For the ZnO particles, the peaks can be unambiguously indexed as shown in the Fig.2 in good agreement with the characteristic hexagonal wurtzite structure of zinc oxide, P63mc

(ICCD Card No: 03-065-3411). However, the presence of two broad diffraction peaks at 33.1° and 59.5° in 2θ , respectively, corresponding to an unidentified impurity, should be noted. Similar diffraction pattern of ZnO nanoparticles with average particle size of 10.0 nm was reported by Kumar et. al. [41]. In our case we found a crystallite size of 22.6 ± 3 nm.

The alginate is an example of an amorphous polymer. In diffractogram of this polymer very broad bump (poor defined peak) from 6 to 30° (at 2θ) is observed. The presence of crystalline phase of an inorganic oxide does not influence significantly on the image of Alg patterns. On the other hand big polymer molecules do not disturb the crystalline structure of oxide's particles (nanocrystals). On the diffractograms of hybrid membranes appears additional peaks originated from the filler, that are more pronounced with the increased load of the oxide (see figure S2 in a ESI file).

The particle size determined by the TEM and BET analysis are in good agreement with the results of the DLS measurement. The differences arise mainly from the limitations of the particular techniques, *e.g.* the shape of the particles or values of the shape factor K in a Scherrer equation. The calculated D50 diameter are presented in the Table 1 and corresponding TEM images are included in an ESI file.

Table 1. The size of synthesized oxide nanoparticles as determined by different techniques.

<i>Oxide</i>	<i>Mean diameter, nm</i>				
	<i>DLS</i>	<i>TEM</i>		<i>BET</i>	<i>XRD*</i>
		<i>D_n50</i>	<i>D_v50</i>		
Fe ₃ O ₄	17.2	14	16.5	13.6	42 ± 7.5
Ag ₂ O	22.6	15	26	18.3	19.2 ± 4.5
ZnO	16.9	14	15	12.4	22.6 ± 3

*crystallite size

3.1.3 Morphological analysis

Fig. 3 shows the SEM images of AlgCa membranes with different types of metal oxide for 10 wt% filler content. The surface morphology of sodium alginate membranes observed by SEM revealed that both the pristine and hybrid sodium alginate membranes have a homogeneous, dense surface. Generally, in case of metal nanoparticles, the aggregation or dispersion is the major problem to be overcome. For two oxides, *i.e.* Cr₂O₃ and TiO₂, SEM images show some agglomerates of oxide nanoparticles on the membrane surface. In case of titanium oxide, the size of these agglomerates is less than 500 nm in diameter, and for chromium(III) oxide it is usually bigger than 1.2 μm. For membranes with silver, iron and zinc oxides the fillers are not visible on the surface, what suggests their better dispersion within an alginate matrix.

SEM profiles obtained from the 3D Roughness Reconstruction module show that the roughness of all membranes surface is similar. The smoothest surface characterizes the membrane with titanium, zinc and chromium oxides, even though the bigger agglomerates on the surface are observed in case of the titanium and chromium oxides. The average arithmetic deviation of the 3D roughness S_a for these membranes is equal to 360, 408 and 441 nm, respectively. The surface of the membrane containing silver oxide has a slightly higher roughness ($S_a = 513$ nm). The most three-dimensional extended surface is noticed for alginate membranes with magnetite ($S_a = 773$ nm) resulting in a flake-like structure.

Fig.3. SEM images of alginate membranes with 10 wt% of: A - Fe_3O_4 , B - Ag_2O , C - TiO_2 , D - Cr_2O_3 , E – ZnO . Magnification 3000x.

To examine the effect of oxide loading on its distribution inside the polymer matrix and its tendency to aggregation phenomena, a series of SEM images of membranes with an increasing loading of chromium(III) oxide are presented in Figure 4. The Cr_2O_3 forms the primary aggregates of size from 100 nm in the case of the light-filled membrane to 300-400 nm for the higher loaded membranes. Formation of secondary aggregates is easily observed on the surface of membranes with 10 and 15 wt% of oxide. These secondary aggregates have a different shape, from circular to elongated ellipses, with dimensions starting from 1000 nm up to 5000 nm. The percentage of oxide loading in the membrane was confirmed by EDS analysis and presented in Table 2. Such analysis is always affected by an error associated with the measured spots, which can be compensated by mapping from a larger area. The relative error of this measurement is less than 7%.

Figure 4. SEM images of Alg membranes with an increasing loading of chromium(III) oxide

0 – 5 – 10 – 15 wt%

Table 2. EDS determination of the metal oxides content in the hybrid Alg membranes.

Element Number	Element Symbol	Element Name	Oxide concentration as metal, wt%					
			5 wt% in Alg		10 wt% in Alg		15 wt% in Alg	
			EDS	teoretical	EDS	teoretical	EDS	teoretical
22	Ti	Titanium	2.88	3.00	6.12	5.99	8.78	8.99
24	Cr	Chromium	3.32	3.42	6.98	6.84	9.71	10.26
26	Fe	Iron	3.72	3.62	7.03	7.23	11.05	10.85
30	Zn	Zinc	4.08	4.02	8.23	8.03	12.55	12.05
47	Ag	Silver	4.81	4.65	8.92	9.31	13.72	13.96

3.2 The influence of metal oxide particles on transport parameters

The evaluated parameters describing transport properties, *i.e.* flux, ethanol and water permeation coefficients in the pervaporation process through Ca^{2+} cations cross-linked alginate membranes are collected in Table 3.

Table 3. Transport properties of metal oxides loaded alginate membranes.

<i>Metal oxide</i>	<i>Transport parameters</i>	<i>Metal oxide content, wt%</i>			
		<i>0</i>	<i>5</i>	<i>10</i>	<i>15</i>
<i>Iron oxide</i>	<i>Flux, J, kg·m⁻²·h⁻¹</i>	0.71	1.12	1.23	1.33
	<i>Permeation coefficient of ethanol, P_{EiOH}·10⁵, Barrer</i>	0.23	0.28	0.32	0.35
	<i>Permeation coefficient of water, P_{H2O}·10⁵, Barrer</i>	4.83	9.23	12.63	16.89
<i>Silver oxide</i>	<i>Flux, J, kg·m⁻²·h⁻¹</i>	0.71	0.77	0.81	0.97
	<i>Permeation coefficient of ethanol, P_{EiOH}·10⁵, Barrer</i>	0.23	0.25	0.28	0.31
	<i>Permeation coefficient of water, P_{H2O}·10⁵, Barrer</i>	4.83	5.03	7.02	7.59
<i>Titanium oxide</i>	<i>Flux, J, kg·m⁻²·h⁻¹</i>	0.71	0.85	0.92	1.09
	<i>Permeation coefficient of ethanol, P_{EiOH}·10⁵, Barrer</i>	0.23	0.30	0.34	0.39
	<i>Permeation coefficient of water, P_{H2O}·10⁵, Barrer</i>	4.83	7.03	7.66	8.56
<i>Chromium oxide</i>	<i>Flux, J, kg·m⁻²·h⁻¹</i>	0.71	1.09	1.13	1.24
	<i>Permeation coefficient of ethanol, P_{EiOH}·10⁵, Barrer</i>	0.23	0.45	0.50	0.64
	<i>Permeation coefficient of water, P_{H2O}·10⁵, Barrer</i>	4.83	9.03	9.53	12.17
<i>Zinc oxide</i>	<i>Flux, J, kg·m⁻²·h⁻¹</i>	0.71	1.14	1.28	1.38
	<i>Permeation coefficient of ethanol, P_{EiOH}·10⁵, Barrer</i>	0.23	0.32	0.34	0.42
	<i>Permeation coefficient of water, P_{H2O}·10⁵, Barrer</i>	4.83	9.49	12.75	15.30

The presence of metal oxide particles in polymer matrix has been proven to have a significant impact on the transport properties of water and ethanol molecules. It was found that fluxes, both water and ethanol permeation coefficients gradually increase with higher loading of

metal oxide particles (see Fig. 5). In case of the overall flux, the highest values are reached for alginate membranes with zinc, iron and chromium oxides. The greatest value is found for 15 wt% of zinc oxide loaded membrane and equals $1.38 \text{ kg}\cdot\text{m}^{-2}\cdot\text{h}^{-1}$. Similar phenomenon of increase in the flux in the presence of zinc oxide addition was observed by Wang et al. for cellulose acetate membranes filled with ZnO and Al₂O₃ particles [42]. The observed increase in the flux after the addition of zinc oxide was explained by the increase of solubility of methanol due to the strong interaction between alcohol molecules and the hydroxyl group on the surface of ZnO oxide. In the case of ethanol/water mixture, the similar should occur in the presence of ZnO, namely the increase in the solubility of ethanol is supposed to take place on the surface of this oxide. The permeation coefficient of water for the pristine membrane is equal to 4.83 Barrer and is twenty one times higher than the permeation coefficient of ethanol. The presence of metal oxide particles affects the further enlargement of difference between permeation coefficients of both components of mixture being separated. This trend is characteristic for all studied oxides but in case of zinc and iron oxides the highest difference between permeation coefficients of water and ethanol is observed for membrane containing the greatest amount of oxides, *e.g.* in case of 15 wt% of magnetite attains 48.26 times.

Fig. 5. The variation of measured total flux for alginate membranes with increasing metal oxide content.

3.3 The influence of metal oxide particles on membrane effectiveness parameters of pervaporation performance

Table 4 presents performance efficiency indexes calculated from the pervaporative tests of ethanol dehydration. The results show that the pristine alginate membrane exhibits a natural selectivity and the process of dehydration of ethanol by using the pristine membrane is also possible. In this case, selectivity coefficient, separation factor ($\alpha_{\text{H}_2\text{O}/\text{EtOH}}$) and *PSI* are equal to 21.00, 26.48 and $18.15 \text{ kg}\cdot\text{m}^{-2}\cdot\text{h}^{-1}$, respectively. However, after addition of oxide particles the considered parameters are changed. In all cases, the *PSI* and $\alpha_{\text{H}_2\text{O}/\text{EtOH}}$ increase; for alginate membranes filled with 5 wt% of titanium or chromium oxide particles, the evaluated separation factor reaches the values of 33.29 and 28.32, respectively. Above the 5 wt% level of TiO_2 and Cr_2O_3 content, the larger voids formation due to the phase separation between an organic moiety and inorganic particles is postulated. Water and ethanol molecules can non-selectively permeate through these voids, resulting in a decreased water permselectivity of

hybrid membranes. Yang et al. investigated the pervaporative dehydration of ethanol on similar chitosan membranes filled with TiO₂. At first the membrane's sorption selectivity increased, then decreased if the TiO₂ content increase. When the TiO₂ content was greater than 8 wt% for CS/TiO₂-R(1) and 6 wt% for CS/TiO₂-R(2) membrane, respectively, the decrease in separation processes was obvious [43].

Table 4. Pervaporative dehydration effectiveness of ethanol on alginate membranes with metal oxides.

<i>Metal oxides</i>	<i>Transport parameters</i>	<i>Metal oxide content, wt%</i>			
		<i>0</i>	<i>5</i>	<i>10</i>	<i>15</i>
<i>Iron oxide</i>	<i>Selectivity coefficient S_c</i>	21.00	32.96	39.47	48.26
	<i>Separation factor, α_{H₂O/EtOH}</i>	26.48	34.30	47.07	58.76
	<i>Pervaporation separation index PSI, kg·m⁻²·h⁻¹</i>	18.15	37.34	56.79	76.59
<i>Silver oxide</i>	<i>Selectivity coefficient S_c</i>	21.00	20.12	25.07	24.48
	<i>Separation factor, α_{H₂O/EtOH}</i>	26.48	32.89	33.78	31.42
	<i>Pervaporation separation index PSI, kg·m⁻²·h⁻¹</i>	18.15	24.55	26.55	29.51
<i>Titanium oxide</i>	<i>Selectivity coefficient S_c</i>	21.00	23.43	22.53	21.95
	<i>Separation factor, α_{H₂O/EtOH}</i>	26.48	33.29	32.19	30.14
	<i>Pervaporation separation index PSI, kg·m⁻²·h⁻¹</i>	18.15	27.45	28.69	31.76
<i>Chromium oxide</i>	<i>Selectivity coefficient S_c</i>	21.00	20.06	19.06	19.02
	<i>Separation factor, α_{H₂O/EtOH}</i>	26.48	28.32	27.77	25.16
	<i>Pervaporation separation index PSI, kg·m⁻²·h⁻¹</i>	18.15	29.78	30.25	29.96
<i>Zinc oxide</i>	<i>Selectivity coefficient S_c</i>	21.00	29.66	37.50	36.43
	<i>Separation factor, α_{H₂O/EtOH}</i>	26.48	28.24	30.28	27.45
	<i>Pervaporation separation index PSI, kg·m⁻²·h⁻¹</i>	18.15	31.05	37.48	36.50

In case of alginate membranes filled with silver and zinc oxides, the highest separation efficiency was achieved for 10 wt% of oxides content. Selectivity coefficient, separation factor and *PSI* of membrane with Ag₂O were equal to 25.07, 33.78 and 26.55 kg·m⁻²·h⁻¹, respectively, and for alginate membrane with ZnO reached correspondingly the values of 37.50, 30.28 and 37.48 kg·m⁻²·h⁻¹. Wang et al. reported improved permeation flux and separation factor of the methanol/MTBE mixture subjected to the pervaporative separation on the cellulose acetate membranes, filled with zinc oxide and alumina particles. Comparing with the pristine cellulose acetate membrane, the maximum separation factor was achieved for blended membrane filled with ZnO, which well corresponds to the our results obtained for alginate membranes [42].

The highest values of selectivity coefficient, separation factor and *PSI* were obtained for alginate membranes filled with magnetite. In contrast to other considered membranes, the addition of iron oxide increase all evaluated performance factors. Moreover, this trend grows monotonically even for higher and higher oxide content, wherefore the highest values of a selectivity coefficient, separation factor and *PSI* were attained for alginate membrane with 15 wt% of magnetite. In this case, the separation factor was equal to 58.76 and was about two times higher than that of pristine one (Fig.6). In the case of membranes filled with iron oxide, the magnetic properties of the filler enhance the separation process of ethanol/water mixture. The positive effect of magnetic field, both apparent and external, on the separation efficiency has been already postulated and described in the literature [30, 44]. All substances have specific magnetic characteristics due to the spin and orbital magnetic moment of their electrons and nuclei forming the molecules. The diamagnetic characteristic of pure water and ethanol differ from each other and, furthermore, the magnetic moment of their mixture shows a concentration dependence. However, the variation in magnetic moment differs from the characteristics expected from the pure components [45]. It is considered that water and

ethanol form a complex clustered structure due to the extended, dynamic hydrogen-bonding network with the picoseconds rearrangement time scale. In particular, at higher concentrations of ethanol, the structure with small water clusters with restricted freedom of the spatial arrangement are formed, leading to the reduction of magnetic moment. The changes in the hydrogen bonds network with a modification of the inter- and intraclusters interactions, and hence on the magnetic field, have a clear influence on the physicochemical properties of liquid water [46]. The presence of magnetic nanoparticles in membrane modifies the dynamic magnetic properties of water and ethanol mixture. In terms of a small magnetic field generated by Fe₃O₄ particles the rotation of molecules with intrinsic polarization, generates a very small magnetic moment proportional to the ring currents. The positive contribution of polarization paramagnetism term may be responsible for the more effective separation of the water/ethanol mixture due to the induced changes in the structure of water clusters arrangement.

Fig. 6. The variation of evaluated separation factors $\alpha_{H_2O/EtOH}$ with increasing metal oxide content in alginate membranes.

Fig. 7 shows the relation between metal oxide particles content and *PSI*. As it can be seen, the value of pervaporation separation index for alginate membranes with silver, titanium, chromium and zinc oxide particles are very similar and varying from 29.96 to 36.50 for 15 wt% of metal oxide particles. This may be due to the fact that the incorporation of metal oxide particles induces the specific interaction between water molecules and metal oxide particles in the hybrid membranes [47]. Therefore, the adsorption of hybrid membranes towards water molecules increased accordingly. Another behaviour can be observed in case of the iron oxide particles loaded in an alginate membrane. The observed growth is rather violent and the resulting *PSI* values are far outweigh the values obtained for the membranes with other oxides. For the alginate membrane filled with 15 wt% of magnetite content, the *PSI* reaches the value of 76.59. The similar relation is noticed for the separation factor (Fig. 6). For alginate membranes filled with silver, titanium, chromium and zinc oxide particles, the highest values of separation factor are obtained for 5 and 10 wt% of metal oxide particles. The following addition of a filler into the polymer matrix results in the decrease of selectivity of investigated membranes because of the free spaces occurring between organic and inorganic components and allowing easier movement of both water and ethanol. Opposite situation is observed in case of the magnetite loaded alginate membranes. Addition of iron oxide particles into the polymer matrix induces a continuous increase of separation factor to reach the large value of 58.76 for 15 wt% of ferroferric oxide particles loaded.

Fig. 7. The variation of evaluated pervaporation separation index PSI with increasing metal oxide content in alginate membranes.

3.4 Comparison between alginate membranes filled with different metal oxide particles

The hierarchical cluster analysis supports grouping of investigated objects into relatively homogeneous clusters based on their features. This algorithm moves different objects between clusters, gradually joining or dividing them, until they are optimized for intra- and inter-cluster variation. Fig. 8 presents the resulting dendrogram of performed hierarchical cluster analysis of investigated membranes with different metal oxide particles and oxide content using evaluated values of transport (flux, water and ethanol permeation coefficients) and membrane effectiveness parameters (selectivity coefficient, separation factor and PSI) as variables. In general, the generated dendrogram shows the linkage points at which the clusters are linked at increasing levels of dissimilarity. Based on the hierarchical agglomerative cluster analysis, four clusters can be distinguished. The Sum of Squared Error (SSE) was used to measure the correctness of a clustering process. The obtained SSE values less than 5 %

proved that the analysis process was conducted properly. The first one contains pristine alginate membrane and membranes with 5, 10 and 15 wt% of Ag₂O and 5, 10 wt% of TiO₂. Taking into account the whole evaluated parameters and the assignments of mentioned hybrid membranes to the same group as pristine membrane, it can be said that these membranes do not show any significant improvement in the transport and separation properties compared to those of the pristine alginate membrane.

The second cluster includes four kinds of alginate membranes: 5, 10 and 15 wt% of Cr₂O₃ and 15 wt% of TiO₂. In comparison with the first group, larger average values of evaluated parameters are observed, with an average increase about 15 %. Higher values of transport and membrane effectiveness parameters are reached for the third cluster. This group contains four kinds of hybrid membranes: 5 wt% of iron oxide particles and 5, 10 and 15 wt% of zinc oxide particles. In this case, the average increase is about 50 % compared with the first cluster. Finally, the best results are obtained for alginate membranes with 10 and 15 wt% of magnetite (fourth group). Compared with the pristine membrane, the evaluated parameters are about two times higher.

Fig. 8. Hierarchical agglomerative cluster analysis dendrogram with four distinguished clusters of investigated AlgCa membranes based on the evaluated transport and effectiveness parameters.

Fig.9 compares the values of flux, water and ethanol permeation coefficient, selectivity coefficient, separation factor and *PSI* of the four groups distinguished during the hierarchical agglomerative cluster analysis. As it can be seen, the differences between the four separated clusters are lower in case of the transport parameters than in the case of the parameters characterizing the efficiency of the membrane. For the evaluated values of transport, the values of ethanol permeation coefficients are very similar. Another situation is observed in the case of the values of the water permeation coefficients. Passing from the first to the fourth cluster, the higher values of this parameter are obtained what means that more water molecules penetrate through the investigated membranes. Considering membrane

effectiveness parameters it can be seen that the values of separation factors are similar for the first three groups and evaluated values of selectivity coefficients are nearly the same for the first two clusters. The values of *PSI* rise from the first to fourth cluster, but this increase is not uniform. In case of the first three groups the observed difference is not big. The significant difference is noticed only in case of the fourth cluster. Furthermore, for the fourth cluster, the values of selectivity coefficient, separation factor and *PSI* reach the highest values.

It can be concluded that the particle size does not significantly affect the hybrid membrane's separation properties. In contrary, the properties of membrane filler, *i.e.* the affinity to the water molecules, and other collateral properties such as, magnetization, have a major influence on the evaluated parameters. Toledo et al. [45] studied the influence of a magnetic field on the interactions of the water molecules using theoretical calculations and the alterations on the physicochemical properties, through experimental measures of vaporization enthalpy, viscosity and surface tension. It was noticed that the magnetic field weakened the stronger intra clusters hydrogen bonds, breaking the larger clusters on the smaller ones with stronger inter cluster hydrogen bonds. Smaller clusters of water molecules can easier penetrate through the membrane and thus may be responsible for the more effective separation. Hence, magnetite is proved to be the best filler of investigated hybrid membrane for which the best separation of ethanol/water mixture is obtained.

Fig.9. Variability of analysed separation effectiveness parameters for each distinguished cluster group.

4. Conclusions

The paper presents the results of water/ethanol mixture pervaporation studies on alginate membranes loaded with five different metal oxide particles, including two commercial, *i.e.* TiO₂ and Cr₂O₃, and three synthesised by hydrolysis/co-precipitation method, *i.e.* Fe₃O₄, ZnO and Ag₂O.

The presence of metal oxide in the polymer matrix has a significant impact on the transport properties of water and ethanol particles, therefore, makes such membranes particularly appropriate for ethanol dehydration in such application as a biofuel production by *PV* separation with economically reasonable high flux and good selectivity. The insertion of metal oxide particles improves the transport characteristics by increasing fluxes (*e.g.* zinc

oxide loaded membrane) and separation factors (*e.g.* magnetite loaded membrane). In addition, considering the possibility of the use of prepared membranes in industrial applications, the separation properties were expressed through the separation factor and *PSI*. For a membrane filled with magnetite there is a continuous improvement with increasing the oxide content, while for the others a saturation is observed for concentration between 5 and 10 wt% of metal oxides. The separation effectiveness depends mainly on the nature of the filler, and especially magnetic particles of iron oxide proved to be the most effective ones.

Based on their PV ethanol dehydration efficiency, the investigated membranes were statistically classified into four groups, using the hierarchical agglomerative cluster analysis. The hierarchical cluster analysis shows that values of transport parameters (flux and permeation coefficient of ethanol) for all isolated clusters are very similar. By contrast, they show some differences concerning the permeation coefficient of water and factors related to the PV effectiveness. Finally, the best performances are obtained for two alginate membranes filled with magnetite particles, both belonging to the fourth cluster. Indeed, for alginate membranes containing 10 and 15 wt% of magnetite *PSI* has been multiplied by a factor 4 compared to that of the pristine membrane by reaching the values of 56.79 and 76.59, respectively.

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